

PROVISION OF HUMAN RIGHTS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

Ramatov Jumaniyoz Sultanovich. Head of the Department of
Social Sciences, Professor

Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. Doctor of Philosophy

ANNOTATION

In the article, the issue of ensuring human rights in Uzbekistan, its indicators, religious and political views. Protection of human rights at the national level with the help of relevant legal documents, through the independent judicial authority, legalization and implementation of individual guarantees of protection means, international agreements on human rights and issues such as protection and promotion of human rights are analyzed.

Key words: Human rights, conscience, person, property, freedom of speech, pluralism.

As we all know, in the last four years, a number of changes have been noticed in the issue of ensuring human rights in our country, as well as in all areas. Positive changes in conscience, personality, property and freedom of speech, pluralism, diversity of political views and other issues began to be seen. In this regard, the indicators of Uzbekistan have changed significantly in international rankings. Thousands of our compatriots, who were deprived of freedom for long periods of time due to their religious and political views, returned to their families. Tens of thousands of stateless persons who have been living in this country for many years were given passports of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Relations with neighboring and brotherly, near and far foreign countries have improved. Uzbekistan again came to the attention of the world in every aspect.

Uzbekistan has joined more than 80 international documents on human rights,

including 6 basic UN treaties and 4 optional protocols. In order to further develop the field of human rights in the country, the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights and the Roadmap for its implementation were approved by the Presidential Decree on June 22, 2020. Based on the decision of the United Nations General Assembly on October 13, 2020, Uzbekistan was elected to the UN Human Rights Council for a three-year term for the first time in history with a majority vote. Now Uzbekistan operates as one of the 47 member states of the UN Human Rights Council for a period of three years. If we turn to our recent history, it is known that Uzbekistan began to regard human interests, rights and fundamental freedoms as the highest values after gaining independence. A clear example of this is the fact that Uzbekistan became a member of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on September 30, 1991. Because, from the first days of independence, these three countries set themselves the goal of building a legal democratic state based on a free market economy, and in this way, the priority of universal values recognized by the world community was recognized. The International Bill of Human Rights is the most basic set of documents adopted for the protection of human rights, and it serves as a basis for all subsequent documents adopted in this field. The International Bill of Human Rights includes the main documents in the field of human rights. These international instruments include: Protection of human rights at the national level. In the second half of the 20th century, many countries became parties to major international human rights treaties. Since these documents impose legal obligations on the implementation of norms in the field of human rights, the norms in this field have been raised to the level of obligations that are implemented on an international scale. International treaties on human rights cover the mutual relations of certain persons and the relations between certain persons and the state. Therefore, the protection and promotion of human rights is primarily an internal duty of the state, and the responsibility for its implementation falls on each state. Protection of human

rights on a national scale is provided by means of the relevant legal documents, through the independent judicial authority, through the legalization and implementation of individual guarantees of the means of protection, as well as through the establishment of democratic institutions. In addition, there are campaigns developed and implemented at the national and local level, taking into account local conditions and traditions, which are recognized as effective activities that have an educational and informative nature. The problem of effective protection of human rights on a national scale is of great interest in the world, especially at the beginning of the 21st century. The emergence or restoration of democratic forms of governance in many countries indicates the importance of the role played by democratic institutions in providing the legal and political foundations that form the core of human rights. Thus, it is becoming increasingly evident that the effective implementation of human rights primarily requires the creation of national infrastructures for the promotion and protection of these rights. In the following years, in many countries of the world, institutions with specific tasks related to the protection of human rights were established. Although the tasks of such institutions differ from country to country, they all have one common goal. For this reason, they are considered national institutions for the promotion and protection of human rights. Human rights representative of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Institute of Human Rights Representative (Ombudsman) under the Parliament was established at the initiative of the 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the first session of the Oliy Majlis, and according to the decision of the Oliy Majlis on May 6, 1995, in order to support the representative in his presence in the exemplary implementation of human rights tasks, to observe the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens Commission was established. In order to further increase the effectiveness of the reforms carried out in our country, to create conditions for the all-round and rapid development of the state and society, to implement the

priority directions for the modernization of our country and the liberalization of all spheres of life, comprehensive study of the current issues that make the population and entrepreneurs think, current legislation, law Action strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, which was developed as a result of the analysis of application practice and advanced foreign experience, as well as a broad public discussion. It was approved by Decree No. PF-4947. So, we can say that along with the building of a legal democratic society, it shows that the legal consciousness and culture of the citizens has increased. Also, at present, there are several agencies in our republic dealing with issues of compliance and protection of human rights. Two of them are legislative, one is executive and one is a non-governmental body. For example, in the first year of work of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1995, the representative body of the Oliy Majlis on Human Rights was established, and the Commission dealing with human rights and freedom was established under its authority. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic was established. The National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an interagency analysis, clarification and coordination body, that is, this body coordinates the activities of state management bodies in the field of human rights, develops a national plan of work in the field of human rights, prepares national reports on the protection of human rights in Uzbekistan, and for civil servants creates an information base in the field of human rights protection, educates them, gives advice, conducts investigations. The main goal of the center is to develop and implement the National Activity Program in the field of Human Rights - a multifaceted system of protection of rights and freedoms, including: improvement of legislation in the field of Human Rights by comprehensively solving the priority tasks; • Provision of legal aid and protection of human rights through court proceedings; • Creation of a system of out-of-court

protection of human rights; • Development of a strategy to protect the rights of different categories of persons; • Ensuring freedom of information as a guarantee of compliance with human rights; Organization of a multi-purpose system of education in the field of human rights - from individual specialized courses to public information - familiarization programs • Coordination of the activities of ministries, committees, offices and institutions within the framework of the executive power in the field of human rights: formation of access routes to the international community based on the development of the system of human rights and freedoms in the Republic of Uzbekistan . The ideological basis of the center's activity program is the universal principles of the development of legal culture contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The scientific planning of the development of the ideology of the legal state envisages the creation of a national concept of human rights protection. This convention should reflect the experience of centuries-old legal culture of the East, the lifestyle traditions of our great ancestors. The activity of the Center to create a national concept of human rights protection is an important theoretical part of the national program of actions in the field of human rights, the beginning of the stage of fundamental changes in the socio-political life of the country. The National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an interagency analysis, clarification and coordination body, that is, this body coordinates the activities of state management bodies in the field of human rights, develops a national plan of work in the field of human rights, prepares national reports on the protection of human rights in Uzbekistan, and for civil servants creates an information base in the field of human rights protection, trains them, gives advice, conducts propaganda.

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